

Effect of the Oxy-fuel Combustion of Toluene on Pollutant Emissions

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Introduction

- Every second, humanity releases more than 1,300 tonnes of CO₂ into the atmosphere - that's over 40 billion tonnes every year¹.

- Oxy-combustion is a promising clean combustion technology designed to facilitate carbon capture and storage (CCS).
- The IPCC has identified BECCS (**B**io**E**nergy **C**arbon **C**apture and **S**torage) as one of the very few technologies capable of achieving net-negative CO₂ emissions.
- This work is part of the OXY3C (**C**arbon **C**apture by eco-efficient **O**xy-**C**ombustion processes) project in the PEPR SPLEEN.
- The work explores the combustion chemistry of biomass tar surrogates under oxy-combustion conditions.

¹P. Friedlingstein *et al.*, "Global Carbon Budget 2023," *Earth System Science Data*, vol. 15, no. 12, pp. 5301–5369, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.5194/essd-15-5301-2023.

Objectives of the work

To investigate the chemical kinetics of **soot precursors** and **soot particles** obtained from toluene

- They are produced due to incomplete fuel combustion.
- PAHs and OPAHs are known for their toxicity.
- Soot particles contribute to global warming and fine particle toxicity.

Inhalation
Ingestion
or dermal exposure

Carcinogenic
Genotoxic
DNA damage

Jet-stirred reactor

Fuel-rich flame

Temperature

PAHs: Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons

OPAHs: Oxygenated Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons

Jet-stirred reactor setup

- O₂ — Pyrolysis

— Oxidative Pyrolysis ($\Phi = 3.2$)

Addition of a small, determined amount of O₂

Making the process autothermal

Jet-stirred reactor

Operates under steady-state conditions

Homogeneous temperature, pressure, and composition ($T = 650-1200\text{K}$, $P = 800\text{ Torr}$, $\tau = 2\text{ sec}$, $x = 0.375\%$)

- The gases are premixed and preheated before they reach the reactor.
- A pressure regulatory valve is placed downstream the reactor to control the pressure inside the reactor.
- The outlet mixture of the reactor is studied by gas chromatography with multiple detectors.

CFC: Cori flow controller, MFC: Mass flow controller, CEM: Controlled evaporator mixer, TC: Temperature control, TR: Temperature reading, PR: Pressure reading, : Heating resistance

Characterization of species

- The chemical species are eluted from the chromatographic column according to their interaction with the stationary phase of the column.
- Every peak corresponds to a chemical species.
- The peak area (A_i) is converted to mole fraction (x_i).

Quantification and identification of species obtained from JSR

- Using advanced gas chromatographic analytical techniques

Quantification

GC-TCD

GC-FID

GC-FID

H₂, CO₂, CO, O₂, CH₄

C₁-C₅ species
and MAHs
(Benzene,
toluene,
ethylbenzene,
...)

PAHs and OPAHs

Identification

GC-MS

Online
sampling

MAHs

Offline
sampling

PAHs and OPAHs

GC: Gas chromatography
TCD: Thermal conductivity detector
FID: Flame ionization detector
MS: Mass spectrometer

Quantification and identification of species

- Section of a chromatogram obtained during the pyrolysis of toluene with CO₂ at 1175K (~80% conversion)
- Multiple peaks highlighting the complex chemistry

Pyrolysis of Toluene

➤ A total of 43 chemical species were identified in the pyrolysis of toluene, including 33 aromatic species.

Oxidative pyrolysis of Toluene

➤ A total of 45 chemical species were identified in the oxidative pyrolysis of toluene, including 30 aromatic species.

Burner setup

- A laminar, premixed, fuel-rich flame was investigated at atmospheric pressure.
- The flame is stabilized on a Holthius burner.

Toluene = 0.033
 CH₄ = 0.185
 O₂ = 0.332
 CO₂ = 0.3375
 H₂O = 0.1125

Dilution = 45%

$\Phi = 2$

Φ : Equivalence ratio

Sampling setup

- Gas sampling using a quartz microprobe.

Quantification and identification of flame species

➤ Using advanced gas chromatographic analytical techniques

Quantification

GC-TCD-FID SCION equipped with **SPT**

CO₂,
CO, O₂ C₁-C₄
species PAHs
and
OPAHs

Identification

GC-MS
Agilent

GC-MS SCION equipped with **SPT**

C₁-C₄ species and MAHs

PAHs and OPAHs

GC: Gas chromatography
TCD: Thermal conductivity detector
FID: Flame ionization detector
MS: Mass spectrometer
SPT: Sample Pre-concentration Trap

Selection of the identified PAHs/OPAHs

- A total of 70 chemical species, including 55 aromatic species, varying between MAHs, PAHs, and OPAHs, were identified.

*HAB: Height above the burner

Mole fraction profile of major species

Mole fraction profiles of minor species

Determination of the soot volume fraction

- The ratio of the volume occupied by soot particles to the total volume.
- Cavity Ring-Down Extinction (CRDE) is a powerful quantitative technique to determine the soot volume fraction.
- It is based on the principle of light extinction. (**Beer-Lambert law**)
- The setup is composed of a laser source, a resonant optical cavity, two highly reflective mirrors, a PMT, and an oscilloscope.

$$I = I_0 e^{-k^{ext} \cdot l}$$

$$\overline{k_\lambda^{ext} l} = \frac{d}{c} \left(\frac{1}{\tau_{soot}} - \frac{1}{\tau_0} \right)$$

- c : speed of light in vacuum
- d : diameter of the flame = 6 cm
- l : length of the cavity = 40 cm
- L : total loss per path in the cavity
- τ_0 : decay time in a clean cavity
- τ : decay time in the presence of soot

Determination of the soot volume fraction

- The soot volume fraction can be determined from the total soot extinction.
- The SVF increases at higher HABs.

HAB = 14 mm

$$f_v = \frac{\overline{k_\lambda^{ext}} \lambda}{6\pi E(m)}$$

f_v : soot volume fraction
 $E(m)$: soot absorption function = 0.3
 m : refractive index
 k_{ext} : soot extinction coefficient
 λ : wavelength

Conclusions

- This study explores the combustion chemistry of toluene in fuel-rich flames and in a JSR under oxy-combustion environment.
- A large variety of chemical species was identified, highlighting the rich and complex chemistry involved.
- The soot volume fraction increases with height above the burner (HAB), indicating that soot particles continue to grow and accumulate as combustion products rise through the flame.
- This work contributes to the understanding of pollutant formation under oxy-combustion conditions, which is a key technology for carbon capture and storage (CCS). The results provide essential chemical-kinetics data to support the development of cleaner, more efficient combustion processes within the framework of the OXY3C project.

Thank you for your attention!

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